
WORK CONDITIONS AS CORRELATES OF TEACHERS JOB COMMITMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract

The study examined work conditions as correlates of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a correlation research design. The population of the study consisted of 5,412 respondents which comprised 263 principals' and 5,149 teachers' in the 263 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample of this study comprised 803 respondents which consisted of 263 principals' and 540 teachers' randomly drawn from the population. This study adopted stratified and simple random sampling techniques. The instruments for data collection were two questionnaires structured by the researcher, titled Work Conditions Questionnaire (WCQ), and Teachers Job Commitment Questionnaires (TJCQ). These instruments were subjected to face and construct validation by three experts, two from Educational Management and one from Measurement and Evaluation, all from Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State. The construct validity of the instruments was also established. Cronbach Alpha method was used to determine the reliabilities of the instruments. The reliability yielded the average coefficient value of 0.85 for work conditions questionnaire and 0.85 for teachers' job commitment questionnaire which was considered adequate for the study. Eight hundred and three (803) copies of questionnaires were administered by the researcher with six briefed research-assistants by direct administration and collected on the spot. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer the research questions while the Hypotheses were tested using test of significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. After analyzing the data of the study, the following findings were discovered: that there exist a strong positive and significant relationship between school facilities and a strong positive and significant relationship between organizational culture and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State. Based on the above findings, it was concluded that work conditions are positive and significant correlates of teachers' job commitment. It was recommended among others that: Government should provide adequate school facilities since provision of adequate facilities, equipment and maintenance help teachers to be committed to their job.

Keywords: Work Conditions, Teachers, Job Commitment, School Facilities, Organizational Culture

Introduction

Education has intrinsic and extrinsic values to both individuals and the society at large. Ugwu (2018) affirmed that education improves the development of any nation. It is through the system of education that every child is inculcated the sense of the acceptable group behaviour. It brings about conformity with the life of the society in which they live. It is designed to guide and direct the child in acquiring a culture and moulding his behaviour in the ways of the community. Education is divided into primary, secondary and tertiary levels. National Policy on Education (2014) broadly stated that secondary school education aims at preparing individuals for useful living within the society and for higher education. All these gigantic objectives can only be achieved with committed teachers.

Commitment is a psychological bond with an organization in which people pledge allegiance to its beliefs and objectives. The emotional tie that teachers have with their work is referred to as teacher commitment. One of the most important aspects in effective teaching has been identified as teacher commitment. As a result, teachers with a high level of commitment can make a difference in their students' learning and accomplishment. Committed instructors invest in the school where they work and devote their time and energy to promote it. Teacher commitment is linked to providing a successful learning environment in which students improve their talents and achieve greater success. Teacher commitment is an internal energy that motivates teachers to do better on the job (Tsui & Cheng, in Altun, 2017). Commitment refers to an individual's attraction and attachment to the work and the organization (Ofoegbu, 2014). It refers to the socio-psychological bonding of an individual to his group or organization, its goals and values or to his occupation and profession. It could manifest in three ways, that is, affective, normative and continuance, and each type of commitment ties the individual to the organization in different ways and will differently affect the manner in which the employee conducts themselves in the workplace (Ofoegbu, 2014).

Teachers' commitment to efficiency, productivity and effectiveness in teaching and learning would translate into better school examination results and higher pass rates for learners. Schools which seek to retain their teachers by building very high organizational commitment are in a better position to reap the benefits of a more dedicated, motivated, punctual and reliable teachers. Teaching is a complex and demanding profession and for teachers to sustain their energy and enthusiasm for work, teachers need to maintain their personal commitment to the job (Day, 2014).

In public secondary school in Anambra State, over the years the poor commitment to duty seemed to have reached an alarming rate with its devastating consequences on the students and the society in general. Over the past few years, public secondary school system has witnessed an alarming rate of brain-drains, industrial conflict, job apathy and loss of commitment to organizational responsibilities (Tsui & Cheng, in Altun, 2017). Some teachers consistently report late for duty; some teachers hardly appear in schools and had poor relations with fellow teachers, among others. Many teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State hardly prepare their scheme of work and lesson plans, and neither conduct sufficient practical lessons or give time for remedial classes for academically weak students (Ofoegbu, 2014). Consequently government has given attention to uplifting the work conditions of teachers, believing that if their morale is improved it will enhance their job commitment. Teachers are also guaranteed retirement benefits, including a monthly pension commensurate with a teacher's rank, salary and length of service, and a gratuity paid at the

beginning of the retirement. Despite all these efforts to enhance work conditions for teachers, their commitment seems to remain low among some teachers.

Ugwu (2018) defined work conditions as a creation by the interaction of employee with their organizational climate, and it includes psychological as well as physical work conditions. Therefore, the study defined work conditions as the work environment and aspects of a teacher's terms and conditions of employment. Due to the mounting pressure from stakeholders, work conditions have become imperative for organizations to take under consideration (Górny, 2017). This is because work condition has emerged as an essential element to boost the energy level with which the employees perform in any work place. Besides, the growing governmental pressure for better work conditions, employees nowadays also tend to demand better work conditions to carry out their work (Kiazad et al., 2019). Poor work conditions tend to influence workers' fulfillment and commitment on the job. Work conditions cover a broad range of issues, from work time (hours of work) rest periods, and work schedules, remuneration, work environment, organizational culture, work load as well as the physical conditions and mental demands that exist in the workplace. This study was focused on school facilities and organizational culture.

School facilities are imperative for teachers' commitment, and these facilities should be comfortable, safe, secure, accessible, well illuminated, well ventilated, and aesthetically pleasing (Ayodele, 2014). School facility consists of not only the physical structure and the variety of building systems, such as mechanical, plumbing, electrical and power, telecommunications, security, and fire suppression systems. School facilities also include furnishings, materials and supplies, equipment and information technology, as well as various aspects of the building grounds, namely, athletic fields, playgrounds, areas for outdoor learning, and vehicular access and parking. Classroom facilities form the corner stone of a good education system. They are essential ingredients in the effort to realize effective teaching and learning outcome. He further asserted that the quality of facilities has impact not only on educational outcomes but on the well-being of students and teachers. Ayodele pointed out that the availability of adequate chairs, desks and other facilities are necessary for the accomplishment of educational goals and objectives. He revealed that effective management of school facilities brings about development of educational programmes and facilitates educational process. It also results to boosting of the morale of teachers and students and enhances the usefulness in the determination of the worth of a school.

School facility is much more than a passive container of the educational process: it is, rather, an integral component of the conditions of learning. The layout and design of a facility contributes to esthetics of the scenery to students, educators, and community members. Depending on the quality of its design and management, the facility can contribute to a sense of ownership, safety and security, personalization and control, privacy as well as sociality, and spaciousness or crowdedness. Emetarom (2014) saw school facilities to include permanent and semi-permanent structures such as machinery, laboratory equipment, the blackboard, teacher's tools and other equipment as well as consumables. In Nigeria, public school enrolment has continued to increase without a corresponding increase in facilities for effective teaching and learning. As a result of underfunding of education in Nigeria, the government has been encouraging proper maintenance of available school facilities. The researcher viewed physical facilities of the school as, the school buildings, classrooms, library, laboratories, toilet facilities, offices and other materials and infrastructures that would likely motivate students towards teaching and learning. In support of this, Hallak (2018)

identified facilities as the main factor contributing to better performance of students and teachers in the school system.

Teachers' commitment could be foreseen from organizational culture in the school, and the culture prevailing in a school may have relationship on the teachers' job commitment. The nature of culture installed in a school potentially drives teachers' feeling at school which could result in noticeable variation of commitment levels. It also implies that when cultural values of an organization match teachers' expectations, teachers feel committed and vice versa (Cameron, 2017).

Organizational culture refers to the beliefs and values that have existed in an organization for a long time. It is a set of values that help people in an organization understand which actions are considered acceptable and which are considered unacceptable (Cameron, 2017). These are specific collection of values and norms that are shared by people and groups in the organizations and that control the way they interact with one another and with stakeholders outside the organization. Organizational culture stands as the center from which all other factors of human resource management are derived (Anas, 2016). Wallach cited in Anas (2016) suggested that individual job commitment and favourable job outcomes, including job satisfaction, propensity to remain with the organization and job involvement depend upon the match between an individual's characteristics and the organization's culture. Organizational culture is a system of shared assumptions, values and beliefs that governs how people behave in organizations. It provides boundaries and guidelines that help members of the organization know the correct way to perform their jobs. The unique culture of an organization creates a distinct atmosphere that is felt by the people who are part of the group and this atmosphere, is known as the culture of an organization (Okorie, 2014). If teachers have negative work conditions and empowerment they are likely to be absent, have stress related illness, and their commitment tend to be low. All the above are mere speculations without empirical back-up, this study therefore, sought to establish work conditions as correlates of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Statement of the Problem

The evidence based on literature showed that most teachers' lack job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State as evidenced in several cases of heightened absenteeism, low morale, lack of interest in the teaching job, poor class attendance and other statutory demands such as preparation of lesson notes. This lack of commitment of teachers is the biggest danger as it leads to absence of fulfillment of school goals and objectives and invariably has resulted in poor performance of students.

This unpleasant development has attracted the attention of researchers and other stakeholders to find solution to this challenge. However, despite all efforts by stakeholders and scholars in improving teachers' commitment, the trend seems to have persisted. The work conditions of teachers appear to fall short of teachers' expectation manifesting in resignations, vacation of post, non-resumption at post after teachers leave of absence and study leave. Teachers' lack of job commitment could be due to poor work conditions variables such as poor school facilities and poor organizational culture.

Furthermore, in Anambra State, there seem to be dearth of empirical studies that investigated work conditions as correlates of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Hence, the researcher deems it necessary to fill the gap. It is

against this backdrop therefore, and in the light of these distasteful circumstances, that this study raises the question: what is the relationship between work conditions with teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study was to examine work conditions as correlates of teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Establish the extent of relationship between school physical facilities and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.
2. Determine the extent of relationship between organizational culture and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the extent of the relationship between school facilities and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the extent of the relationship between organizational culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between school facilities and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant relationship between organizational culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Method

The study adopted a correlational research design. Nworgu (2015) stated that a correlational research design shows the direction and magnitude of the relationship between or among variables in a given study. The research design also provided clues for the proper understanding of patterns of relationships among variables in the study. The area of the study is Anambra State. Anambra State is made up of three senatorial zones namely: Anambra North, Anambra Central, and Anambra South. These three senatorial zones have 21 local government areas. The population of the study consisted of 5,412 respondents comprising 263 principals and 5,149 teachers in the 263 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample for the study consisted of 803 respondents made up of 263 principals and 540 teachers representing 100% of principals and 10% of teachers. Proportionate stratified and simple random techniques were used for drawing the sample for teachers only. In drawing the sample of the study, proportionate stratified and simple random sampling was used to draw the sample for teachers only. The whole population of principals was adopted for the study because it was manageable hence the researcher adopted census method.

The instruments for data collection were two structured questionnaires by the researcher, titled work conditions questionnaire (WCQ) and teacher job commitment questionnaire (TJCQ) with two sections: Section A which contains information on the

demographic variables of the respondents while Section B contained the items eliciting information on work conditions variables and teacher job commitment in line with the purpose of the study, research questions and hypotheses along optional responses, in the following order: Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The second Questionnaire is Teachers' Job Commitment Questionnaire (TJCQ) in one cluster with 20 items eliciting information on teachers' job commitment structured using 4- point type scale weighed as follows: Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

Direct method was used to administer the instruments to respondents by the researcher with the help of six research assistants who were briefed on how to administer and retrieve the instruments on respondents in a one-day consultative meeting during which the researcher acquainted them with the purpose of the study and how to exhibit good human relation during data collection. It was on the spot administration and collection of the instrument where the researcher and research assistant waited for the respondent to fill the Questionnaires and retrieve them immediately. A follow up visit was done to retrieve from those who were not disposed to fill theirs immediately. Eight hundred and three (803) questionnaires were administered and seven hundred and thirty six (736) were retrieved while sixty seven (67) questionnaires were lost on transit representing about 91% return rate and 9% loss. The seven hundred and thirty-six (736) retrieved questionnaires were used for data analysis in this study.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to answer the research questions and test hypotheses was tested at 0 .05 level of significance. In answering the research questions, the coefficient (r) and the size of the relationship was interpreted using Correlation Coefficient based on Schober *et.al* (2018) as shown: .

- ± 0.00 to 0.09 = Negligible Correlation Coefficient
- ± 0.10 to 0.39 = weak Correlation Coefficient
- ± 0.40 to 0.69 = Moderate relationship
- ± 0.70 to 0.89 = Strong relationship
- ± 0.90 to 1.00 = Very strong relationship

The null hypotheses were tested at 0 .05 level of significance and the decision rule is if the P -value is less than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$), REJECT the null hypothesis in favor of the alternative and If the P -value is greater than the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) fail to reject the null hypothesis.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the extent of relationship between school physical facilities and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient analysis on the extent of relationship between school physical facilities and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Correlations		
		School Facilities	Teachers job commitment	Remark
School Facilities	Pearson Correlation	1	0.85**	Strong positive relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00	
	N	736	736	
Teachers job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.85**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00		
	N	736	736	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05level (2-tailed).

The summary result of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient from the Table 1 above showed a strong positive relationship between school physical facilities and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State, with 'r' =0.85** and N =736. This revealed a positive correlation coefficient value of 0 .85 which indicated that there is a strong positive relationship existing between school physical facilities and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: What is the extent of relationship between organizational culture and teacher's job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the extent of relationship between organizational culture and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State?

		Correlations		
		Organizational Culture	Teachers job commitment	Remark
Organizational Culture	Pearson Correlation	1	0.76**	Strong positive relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00	
	N	736	736	
Teachers job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.76**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00		
	N	736	736	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05level (2-tailed).

The summary result of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient from the Table 2 above showed a strong positive relationship between organizational culture and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State, with 'r' =0.76** and N =736. This revealed a positive correlation coefficient value of 0 .76 which indicated that there is a strong positive relationship existing between organizational culture and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between school facilities and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 3: Test of Significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on relationship between school facilities and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

		Correlations		
		School Facilities	Teachers job commitment	Decision
School Facilities	Pearson Correlation	1	0.85**	Significant relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00	
	N	736	736	
Teachers job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.85**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00		
	N	736	736	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05level (2-tailed).

The result of the test of significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient from Table 3 above showed a significant relationship between school facilities and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. with $r = 0.85^{**}$ $n = 736$ and p -value = 0.000. Since p -value (0.000) is less than 0.05, the study rejects the null hypothesis and do not reject the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant relationship between school facilities and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between organizational culture and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Table 4: Test of Significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the relationship between organizational culture and teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

		Correlations		
		Organizational Culture	Teachers job commitment	Decision
Organizational Culture	Pearson Correlation	1	0.76**	Significant relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00	
	N	736	736	
Teachers job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.76**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00		
	N	736	736	

The result of the test of significance of Pearson-Moment Correlation Coefficient from Table 4 above showed a significant relationship between organizational culture and teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State with $r = 0.76^{**}$.n =736 and p-value =0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05, the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between organizational culture and teachers’ job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Discussion

The result of the study indicated that there existed a strong positive and significant relationship between physical facilities and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State. This findings was as a result of principals and teachers agreeing that staff room is well furnished, there are enough places for relaxation in the school, school surroundings are conducive for learning, school has well ventilated classroom, schools’ ICT center has enough gadgets, school has good internet facilities, there is regular electricity supply in the school, there is regular water supply in the school, school has equipped library, school has equipped laboratory for practical. These findings are in consonance with the study of Foluke and Ogunode (2020) who investigated impact of school plant on English Teachers’ job performance and students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in FCT, Abuja, Nigeria. The findings showed that there was a significant relationship between school plant and English language teachers’ job performance in public secondary schools. Also, these findings are in consonance with the study of Jimoh, *et.al* (2017) that investigated the influence of school plant on teachers’ performance in secondary schools in Ile-Oluji Okeigbo Local Government Area of Ondo State and thier results showed that educational equipment, buildings and playgrounds have individual significant influence on teachers’ performance in secondary schools (Fcal = 140.776; 342.606; 24.932, $p < 0.01$) respectively.

Findings from the study on relationship between organizational culture and teachers’ job commitment in Public Secondary Schools showed a strong positive and significant relationship between organizational culture and teachers’ job commitment. Findings showed that organizational culture is exceedingly essential for teachers’ commitment. These findings were as a result of principals and teachers agreeing that teachers are willing to stick their necks out to get job done in good organizational culture, teachers see school as extended family where people seem to share feeling among themselves, good organizational culture help to break barriers among teachers in school, good organizational culture contributes to

loyalty among teachers in school, helps to bond teachers together in school, commitment to the school runs high in good organizational culture, school emphasizes human resource development for teachers in good organizational culture, teachers are very competitive in good organizational culture, leads to goal accomplishment, good organizational culture. These findings are in line with Adonu (2017) who examined the influence of organizational culture on job performance of teachers in secondary schools in Enugu State and the findings showed that organizational culture has a positive and significant influence on teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Enugu State. The finding of this study is in consonance with Amuse and Okafor (2017) who conducted a study on the impact of organizational culture on job satisfaction among university lecturers in South East Nigeria. The study showed that organizational culture has a positive and significant impact on job satisfaction among university lecturers in South East Nigeria. These findings are in line with Masouleh and Allahyari (2017) that investigated the level of the relationship between organizational culture and commitment among faculty members of Islamic Azad University of Rasht Branch, Iran meaning that relationship between organizational culture and commitment was determined to be statistically significant.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, it is concluded that work conditions have strong positive and significant relationship with teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State. Work conditions determine the energy level with which teachers are committed to their job. Work conditions of teachers in public secondary schools particularly in the conduciveness of school facilities and organizational culture, remuneration are needed by teachers to be optimally committed in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made from the findings of this study

1. Government should provide adequate school facilities, since provision of adequate school facilities help teachers to be committed to their job
2. School principals should ensure a good organizational culture for teachers to work collaboratively for successful implementation of communicated intentions towards quality education.

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